

Digital complete denture fabrication in an edentulous patient utilizing Exocad and additive manufacturing: A case report.

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Abstract

Digital denture fabrication has become a transformative approach in prosthodontics, significantly improving accuracy, efficiency, and patient outcomes. This case report outlines the rehabilitation of a completely edentulous patient using a fully digital workflow involving Exocad Computer aided designing (CAD) software and 3D printing. The patient presented to Buddha Institute of Dental Sciences and Hospital, Patna, with edentulism of two years' duration and no significant medical history. A digital impression was obtained, and the denture was designed using Exocad, followed by additive manufacturing using a 3D printer. The final prosthesis demonstrated excellent fit, occlusion, and esthetics with minimal adjustments. This case highlights the potential of digital workflows as a viable alternative to conventional methods in the rehabilitation of edentulous patients.

Keywords: 3D Optical Scanning, Dental Implants, Impression Techniques, Impression Materials, Prosthetic Fit.

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Introduction

The transition from conventional to digital denture fabrication has revolutionized prosthodontics, providing an efficient, reproducible, and patient-friendly solution for edentulous cases. Traditional workflows involve multiple clinical visits and manual steps prone to errors, whereas digital workflows streamline the process with enhanced precision. [1,2] CAD software such as Exocad allows virtual tooth arrangement and baseplate design, and 3D printing ensures dimensional accuracy. [3,4] Digital dentures are not only time-efficient but also reduce patient discomfort and provide consistent results. [5] This report presents a case of a fully digital complete denture fabricated using Exocad and 3D printing in a patient with complete edentulism.

Case presentation

A 52-year-old male patient, presented to the Department of Prosthodontics, Buddha Institute of Dental Sciences and Hospital, Patna, complaining of difficulty in chewing and facial unesthetics smile due to complete edentulism for the past two years (Fig. 1). The patient had no relevant medical history and expressed interest in a digital prosthetic solution. Clinical examination revealed well-healed maxillary and mandibular ridges with sufficient bone support. [6] After discussing treatment options, a digital workflow was planned using Exocad software and 3D printing technology. Primary impressions were recorded using irreversible hydrocolloid and poured with dental stone. Custom tray fabrication done followed by final impression and impression

was poured and cast retrieved, jaw relation recorded and then it was scanned were scanned using a laboratory desktop scanner (Fig. 2), and the data was exported in STL format. The digital impression files were imported into Exocad software, where virtual baseplate and tooth arrangement were completed (Fig. 3 and 4). A monolithic denture design was finalized, ensuring proper occlusion and esthetic alignment (Fig. 5 and 6).^[7,8]

The digital design was transferred to a 3D printer using a biocompatible denture resin. The denture base and teeth were printed as a single unit using stereolithography (SLA) technology (Fig. 7). Post-processing steps included washing, curing, and finishing of the prosthesis.^[9] The final denture was inserted, and occlusion was evaluated using articulating paper (Fig. 8). Minor adjustments were made, and the patient reported excellent comfort, esthetics, and masticatory function (Fig. 9).^[10]

Discussion

Digital dentures provide a promising alternative to conventional prostheses by reducing the number of clinical visits and improving predictability. CAD/CAM systems have been validated for accuracy, and studies have shown that digitally fabricated dentures match or exceed the fit of conventional ones.^[11,12] In this case, Exocad software allowed flexible customization of the tooth arrangement and ensured ideal occlusal balance. The use of 3D printing accelerated the fabrication process and ensured excellent tissue adaptation.^[13]

Research comparing additive and subtractive manufacturing shows that 3D printed dentures have comparable mechanical properties and superior adaptation in undercuts.^[14] However, challenges include printer calibration, resin polymerization accuracy, and potential occlusal discrepancies due to layer-by-layer build

errors.^[15] Despite these limitations, the digital workflow remains a robust tool in modern prosthodontics, especially for edentulous patients seeking rapid rehabilitation.

Conclusion

This case demonstrates the successful application of Exocad software and 3D printing technology for the fabrication of a complete denture. Digital workflows offer enhanced precision, patient comfort, and clinical efficiency. With continued advancements and training, digital dentures will become an integral part of prosthodontic rehabilitation strategies.

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FIGURES

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

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Figure 8

Figure 9